

Reducing end thiol-modified nanocellulose: Bottom-up enzymatic synthesis and use for templated assembly of silver nanoparticles into biocidal composite material

Chao Zhong^a, Krisztina Zajki-Zechmeister^a, Bernd Nidetzky^{a,b,*}

^a Institute of Biotechnology and Biochemical Engineering, Graz University of Technology, NAWI Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria

^b Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology (acib), 8010 Graz, Austria

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ABSTRACT

Nanoparticle-polymer composites are important functional materials but structural control of their assembly is challenging. Owing to its crystalline internal structure and tunable nanoscale morphology, cellulose is promising polymer scaffold for templating such composite materials. Here, we show bottom-up synthesis of reducing end thiol-modified cellulose chains by iterative bi-enzymatic β-1,4-glycosylation of 1-thio-β-D-glucose (10 mM), to a degree of polymerization of ~8 and in a yield of ~41% on the donor substrate (α-D-glucose 1-phosphate, 100 mM). Synthetic cellulose oligomers self-assemble into highly ordered crystalline (cellulose allomorph II) material showing long (micrometers) and thin nanosheet-like morphologies, with thickness of 5–7 nm. Silver nanoparticles were attached selectively and well dispersed on the surface of the thiol-modified cellulose, in excellent yield (≥ 95%) and high loading efficiency (~2.2 g silver/g thiol-cellulose). Examined against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, surface-patterned nanoparticles show excellent biocidal activity. Bottom-up approach by chemical design to a functional cellulose nanocomposite is presented. Synthetic thiol-containing nanocellulose can expand the scope of top-down produced cellulose materials.

1. Introduction

Metal nanoparticle-polymer composites are diverse and versatile functional materials (Balazs, Emrick, & Russell, 2006; Ferhan & Kim, 2016; Shenhar, Norsten, & Rotello, 2005). Due to their particular electronic and (bio)chemical properties, the metal nanoparticles afford unique functionality (e.g., optical, magnetic, dielectric, catalytic or biological) to their polymer composites (Hanemann & Szabó, 2010; Li, Meng, Toprak, Kim, & Muhammed, 2010; Shenhar et al., 2005). This provides the basis for promising applications of such nanocomposites in different fields, ranging from optoelectronics (Faupel, Zaporjtschenko, Strunskus, & Elbahri, 2010), (bio)sensing (Ferhan & Kim, 2016; Shenhar et al., 2005), catalysis (Mahouche-Chergui, Guerrouache, Carbonnier, & Chehimi, 2013; Shenhar et al., 2005; Zhao et al., 2011) to medicine

(Zare & Shabani, 2016). In nanoparticle-polymer composites, the polymer often promotes the controlled assembly of nanoparticles into localized clusters (Mahouche-Chergui et al., 2013; Shenhar et al., 2005). Undesired (random) agglomeration of nanoparticles is thus prevented. Additionally, the polymer can induce ordering and anisotropic orientation of the nanoparticles (Shenhar et al., 2005; Zhang, Han, & Yang, 2010). Polymer-directed assembly is a powerful approach to structurally arrange the dispersed metal nanoparticles into morphologically controlled, functional nanoarchitectures (Ofir, Samanta, & Rotello, 2008; Shenhar et al., 2005; Zhang, Liu, Yao, & Yang, 2012). The polymer templates used are often derived from natural resources, like biopolymers (e.g., DNA (Lan et al., 2013), polysaccharides (Travan et al., 2011)), biomolecular assemblies (e.g., peptides (Song, Wang, & Rosi, 2013), lipids (Goertz, Goyal, Bunker, & Montañó, 2011)) and even

Abbreviations: AFM, atomic force microscopy; ATR-FTIR, attenuated total reflection-Fourier transform infrared; CbP, cellobiose phosphorylase (EC 2.4.1.20); CcCdP, CdP from *Clostridium cellulosi*; CdP, celloextrin phosphorylase (EC 2.4.1.49); CNCs, cellulose nanocrystals; CNFs, cellulose nanofibrils; CuCbP, CbP from *Cellulomonas uda*; DP, degree of polymerization; EDXS, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy; αGlc1-P, α-D-glucose 1-phosphate; LB, Lysogeny broth; MALDI-TOF-MS, matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry; NMR, nuclear magnetic resonance; XRD, X-ray diffraction.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: czhong@tugraz.at (C. Zhong), krisztina.zajki-zechmeister@tugraz.at (K. Zajki-Zechmeister), bernd.nidetzky@tugraz.at (B. Nidetzky).

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viruses (Li & Wang, 2014). The applicability of bio-based templates can be limited, however, due to their low resistance to thermal, mechanical and chemical “stressors” (Sadasiyuni et al., 2020). A biopolymer material showing both high structural stability and controllable nanoscale attributes in the assembly of the metal nanoparticles would be highly desirable. The polysaccharide cellulose offers these characteristics (Klemm, Heublein, Fink, & Bohn, 2005; Moon, Martini, Nairn, Simonson, & Youngblood, 2011) and has therefore drawn considerable interests for use in templating applications with metal nanoparticles.

Among the broad variety of cellulose materials known (Klemm et al., 2005), nanocelluloses are promising in particular to advance a growing number of nanocomposite material applications (Dufresne, 2013; Habibi, Lucia, & Rojas, 2010; Kontturi et al., 2018; Zhang, Zhang, Wu, & Xiao, 2020). Nanocelluloses are highly crystalline, mechanically stable materials which, depending on whether chemical or mechanical processing of natural cellulose has been used for their preparation, are obtained as twisted nanorod-like cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) or cellulose nanofibrils (CNFs), respectively (Dufresne, 2019; Moon et al., 2011). These nanocelluloses display nanoscale lateral dimensions and nanometer to micrometer length (Habibi et al., 2010; Kontturi et al., 2018). By virtue of their high surface area and porosity (Kontturi et al., 2018; Salas, Nypelö, Rodriguez-Abreu, Carrillo, & Rojas, 2014; Zhang et al., 2020), they make excellent candidates for the templating of metal nanoparticles. Tunable surface functionalities of nanocellulose facilitate the nanoparticle assembly via electrostatic or covalent interactions (An, Long, & Ni, 2017; Guo, Filpponen, Su, Laine, & Rojas, 2016). Surface functionalization involves different chemical groups (e.g., sulfate (Lin & Dufresne, 2014; Lokanathan, Uddin, Rojas, & Laine, 2014), carboxylate (He, Zhao, Liu, & Roberts, 2007), amino (Boufi et al., 2011; Guo et al., 2016), and thiol (An et al., 2019) and is typically nonselective positionally. However, CNCs have also been selectively modified at their reducing chain ends, by introducing thiol (Arcot et al., 2013; Arcot, Lundahl, Rojas, & Laine, 2014; Tao, Dufresne, & Lin, 2019) or triazole group (Li et al., 2018). Due to the parallel orientation of their cellulose chains in cellulose allomorph I crystals (O'Sullivan, 1997), the CNCs can thus be derivatized (e.g., with silver (Ag) nanoparticles becoming covalently linked to thiol groups (Arcot et al., 2013)) topo-chemically selective at one end of the nanorod (Heise et al., 2020; Tao, Lavoine, Jiang, Tang, & Lin, 2020). Despite the important advances made in the design of nanocellulose-mediated metal nanoparticle assemblies, there is also concern about the chemically harsh and energy-intensive conditions used in the preparation of suitably functionalized CNCs or CNFs from natural materials. Here, we therefore conceptualized a bottom-up approach that applies enzyme catalysis under mild conditions in water or buffer to the synthesis of reducing-end thiol-modified cellulose chains. These chains, self-assembled from solution into functionalized cellulosic materials, are able to bind the metal nanoparticles with high selectivity. We considered that bottom-up approaches such as the one reported here might represent a powerful adjunct to the existing top-down technologies for the fabrication of metal nanoparticle-nanocellulose hybrids (Kaushik & Moores, 2016). The in vitro self-assembled cellulose typically has cellulose II crystal structure with antiparallel orientation of the cellulose chains (Hiraishi et al., 2009; Kobayashi, Kashiwa, Kawasaki, & Shoda, 1991; Pylkkänen et al., 2020; Serizawa, Kato, Okura, Sawada, & Wada, 2016; Zhong, Luley-Goedl, & Nidetzky, 2019). The antiparallel-chain crystalline organization of the synthetic cellulose provides a unique topochemistry of nanoparticles binding (Nohara, Sawada, Tanaka, & Serizawa, 2019), different from CNCs. Enhanced structural control over the cellulose nanomorphology and the chemical group-directed assembly of the metal nanoparticles might be a distinct advantage of the bottom-up approach (Kobayashi & Makino, 2009; Nidetzky & Zhong, 2020). Biocatalytic synthesis of unmodified and reducing-end modified cellulose chains has been demonstrated using enzymes from different classes, including glycoside hydrolases (Kobayashi et al., 1991), glycosynthases (Fort et al., 2000), glycoside phosphorylases (Nidetzky & Zhong, 2020), and

glycosyltransferases (Purushotham et al., 2016). However, reducing-end thiol-modified cellulose chains, to our knowledge, have never been synthesized enzymatically.

In this study, we demonstrate the iterative β -1,4-glycosylation of 1-thio- β -D-glucose catalyzed by cellobiose phosphorylase (EC 2.4.1.20) and cellodextrin phosphorylase (EC 2.4.1.49), as illustrated in Fig. 1A. Both enzymes use α -D-glucose 1-phosphate (α Glc1-P) as the donor substrate for glycosylation (Zhong & Nidetzky, 2019; Zhong et al., 2019). We analyzed the polymerization reaction by the enzymes to prepare the thiol-modified cellulose in useful synthetic yield at gram scale. We characterized the resulting material structurally and determined its ability to assemble Ag nanoparticles on the solid surface. We evaluated the antibacterial activity of thus prepared nanoparticle-cellulose composite against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Collectively, a bottom-up approach by chemical design to the fabrication of a selectively self-assembled, functional composite of Ag nanoparticles and thiol-containing nanocellulose is presented. Enzymatic polymerization of the reducing-end thiol-modified cellulose chains is the key step. It may be generally useful to expand the scopes of cellulose materials beyond the reach of current top-down technologies.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials

Unless stated, the chemicals used were of highest purity available at Sigma-Aldrich (Vienna, Austria) or Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany). *S. aureus* subsp. *aureus* (strain ATCC 25923) was obtained from the Institute of Environmental Biotechnology at Graz University of Technology.

2.2. Enzymes

Cellobiose phosphorylase (CbP) from *Cellulomonas uda* (CuCbP; GenBank identifier AAQ20920.1) and cellodextrin phosphorylase (CdP) from *Clostridium cellulosi* (CcCdP; GenBank identifier CDZ24361.1) were obtained using reported methods (Zhong et al., 2019). Briefly, the enzymes were produced in *E. coli* BL21-Gold (DE3) and purified to apparent homogeneity via their N-terminal His-tag. Enzyme stock solutions (20 mg/mL) in 50 mM MES buffer (pH 7.0) were stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ without appreciable loss in activity for at least two weeks. Assay for enzyme activity (45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 50 mM MES buffer, pH 7.0) measured the release of phosphate (colorimetric detection) from α Glc1-P (50 mM) upon β -1,4-glucosyl transfer to a suitable acceptor (50 mM) (Zhong et al., 2019). Routinely, glucose was used with CuCbP, cellobiose with CcCdP. In addition, activity with 1-thio- β -D-glucose (50 mM) was determined for each enzyme. Protein was measured with ROTI Quant assay (Carl Roth, Karlsruhe, Germany) referenced against bovine serum albumin.

2.3. Bottom-up synthesis of thiol-modified nanocellulose

Reactions were carried out at 45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 300 rpm agitation, through incubation on a ThermoMixer C (Eppendorf, Vienna, Austria). α Glc1-P (100 mM) and 1-thio- β -D-glucose (10 mM) were used in MES buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0). Reactions applied CcCdP (0.08 mg/mL) alone or CcCdP (0.08 mg/mL) and CuCbP (0.06 mg/mL) in combination. Reaction time (12–48 h) was variable depending on the conditions used. The reference reaction used glucose (10 mM) instead of 1-thio- β -D-glucose and applied CcCdP together with CuCbP as described above.

All reactions yielded insoluble material visible as white precipitate. The insoluble material was centrifuged off (10,000 rpm, 5 min), washed several times with distilled water and stored wet at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. About 0.5 g wet material was lyophilized.

Fig. 1. Strategy for bottom-up preparation of reducing end thiol-modified nanocellulose loaded with Ag nanoparticles. **A)** Linear cascade of cellobiose phosphorylase (CbP) and cellodextrin phosphorylase (CdP) for the synthesis of reducing end thiol-modified crystalline cellulose from 1-thio- β -D-glucose and α Glc1-P. **B)** Graphic illustration of templated assembly of Ag nanoparticles onto the surface of thiol-modified cellulose.

2.4. Material characterization

Atomic force microscopy (AFM). This was done in air, using a Dimension FastScan Bio instrument (Bruker AXS, Karlsruhe, Germany) with a NanoScope V controller in tapping mode at room temperature. Suspension of cellulose in water (approximately 2 mg/mL), in 60 μL , was mounted onto a freshly cleaved mica surface and air-dried overnight. A FastScan-A probe (Bruker AXS, Camarillo, CA, USA) was applied. Set point was chosen to be 80–90% of the free amplitude. Analysis and images processing were done with Gwyddion 2.55 (<http://gwyddion.net/download.php>).

X-ray diffraction (XRD). The diffraction data were obtained for lyophilized cellulose using a D8 Advance powder diffractometer (Bruker AXS). The instrument was applied in Bragg-Brentano geometry using a Bruker LYNXEYE SuperSpeed Detector at room temperature. The instrument was operated at 40 kV and 40 mA, using Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418 \text{ nm}$). Diffraction angles were measured from 5° to 60° 2θ , with a step size of 0.02° 2θ and 5 s per step.

Attenuated total reflection-Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR). Absorption spectra of cellulose suspension ($\sim 4 \text{ mg/mL}$, in water) were obtained at room temperature on a Bruker ALPHA FTIR spectrometer (Bruker Optik, Ettlingen, Germany) using ATR accessory with a diamond window. Spectra were measured in the range $4125\text{--}375 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, with a spectral resolution of 2 cm^{-1} and 128 scans.

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). ^1H NMR spectra of lyophilized cellulose dissolved in 4% NaOD- D_2O (10 mg/mL) were recorded on a Varian Inova-500 NMR spectrometer (Agilent

Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) at 30°C using a VNMRJ 2.2D software. The ^1H NMR spectra were measured at 499.98 MHz on a 5 mm indirect detection PFG-probe. The chemical shifts were recorded relative to D_2O (at $\delta_{\text{H}} 4.8$). All spectral data were analyzed using MestReNova (<https://mestrelab.com>).

Matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF-MS). This was done on a Bruker Autoflex Speed instrument (Bruker Daltonics, Billerica, MA, USA) using FlexControl 3.4 software. The cellulose suspension ($\sim 4 \text{ mg/mL}$, 0.2 μL) was vacuum-dried on a polished steel plate before addition of matrix (0.5 μL of 2% (w/v) 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid in 30% (v/v) acetonitrile) and crystallization again under vacuum. The MS spectra were recorded in the range $700\text{--}2500 \text{ m/z}$ in reflector mode, with detector voltage set at 2217 kV. The spectra were processed with the software Bruker FlexAnalysis 3.3.80 (<https://www.bruker.com>).

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS). Measurements of lyophilized cellulose samples were done using a scanning electron microscope Zeiss Sigma 300 VP (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Jena, Germany) equipped with a X-Max 80 Detector (Silicon drift detector, Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, UK). It was operated at an acceleration voltage of 10 kV in the high vacuum mode.

Element analysis. Carbon (C) and sulfur (S) content (%) in lyophilized cellulose (2 mg) was determined using a dry combustion method on the vario MICRO cube analyzer (Elementar Analysensystem GmbH, Langensfeld, Germany) connected to a thermal conductivity detector. Helium (He) served as flushing and carrier gas.

2.5. Ag nanoparticles

Ag nanoparticles were prepared by a reported protocol based on reduction of silver nitrate (AgNO_3) with sodium citrate (Gakiya-Teruya, Palomino-Marcelo, & Rodriguez-Reyes, 2018). Briefly, the silver nitrate solution (1 mM, 50 mL) in 100 mL glass beaker was firstly heated to the boiling point and sodium citrate (0.35 M) was slowly dripped into the solution (to final concentration of 7 mM). The beaker was covered, the solution was heated with magnetic stirring (200 rpm) for 10 min and cooled down afterwards. The resultant colloidal solution of Ag nanoparticles was stored at 4 °C in the dark (no longer than 2 weeks).

2.6. Preparation of Ag nanoparticle-cellulose composite

Thiol-cellulose (0.05–0.42 mg, dry weight) was initially suspended (on vortex mixer; 2500 rpm, 10 s) into 1 mL freshly prepared colloidal solution of Ag nanoparticles. The suspension was then incubated on a ThermoMixer C (Eppendorf, Vienna, Austria) with an agitation rate of 600 rpm at room temperature. After incubation for certain times (as indicated in *Results and discussion*), the suspension was centrifuged ($1500 \times g$, 1 min). The content of Ag nanoparticles in supernatant was determined. The pellet was collected, washed several times with water, and stored wet at 4 °C. As a control, non-modified cellulose (0.42 mg, dry weight) was used in the same procedure described above. In addition, the stability of Ag nanoparticles on cellulose was measured, by resuspending the pellets for 5 min (on vortex mixer; 2500 rpm) and centrifuging the suspensions ($1500 \times g$, 1 min) immediately afterwards. The increase in Ag nanoparticle content in the supernatant was measured.

The binding efficiency η (%) of Ag nanoparticles on cellulose was calculated as $\eta = 100 \times (\gamma_0 - \gamma) / \gamma_0$, where γ_0 and γ is the Ag nanoparticle content before and after binding, respectively. The Ag nanoparticle concentration in solution was measured by absorbance at 410 nm (Rucha, Mankad, Gupta, & Jha, 2012) in a DU-800 UV/Visible spectrophotometer (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA) at room temperature. A calibration was made based on the original colloidal solution of the Ag nanoparticles (Supplementary material S1).

2.7. Antibacterial activity evaluation

E. coli (strain BL21) and *S. aureus* (strain ATCC 25923) were streaked onto LB (lysogeny broth)-agar and incubated at 37 °C for 12 h. A single colony was picked, transferred into liquid LB medium, and incubated in Erlenmeyer flasks (300 mL; 100 mL medium) at 37 °C overnight. Agitation was at 110 rpm on a ZWY-B3222 orbital shaker (LABWIT Scientific, Blackburn South, Victoria, Australia). The resulting cell suspensions were immediately used for evaluating the antibacterial activity of the Ag nanoparticle samples. The nanoparticle-cellulose composite, prepared by mixing the thiol-cellulose (0.42 mg, dry weight) with 1 mL colloidal solution of Ag nanoparticles for 5 min, was used. The composite (as pellet after centrifugation) was resuspended in water (or buffer), through vortex mixing (2500 rpm) for 30 s, and was used in a well suspended form for the tests.

Agar-plate test. One mL of properly diluted microbial culture ($1-2 \times 10^5$ colony forming units (cfu)/mL) was uniformly distributed on a LB-agar plate. Ten μL of Ag nanoparticle samples (i.e., colloidal solution of Ag nanoparticles; suspension of Ag nanoparticle-cellulose composite) were dripped onto the plates and left drying in air. The control used 10 μL of a thiol-cellulose suspension (0.42 mg/mL; in sterilized water) that lacked Ag nanoparticles. The agar plates were placed at 37 °C for 24 h, and colonies in the area loaded with sample were recorded.

Shake-flask test. Nanoparticle-cellulose composite (0.25 g, wet weight) was added into a 300 mL Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 mL sterilized phosphate buffered saline (0.3 mM, pH 7.2) culture solution with a cell density of approximately 7×10^5 cfu/mL. The flask was incubated at 30 °C and 150 rpm in a CERTOMAT BS-1 shaking incubator

(Sartorius Stedim Biotech, Göttingen, Germany). Samples of 20 μL were periodically taken (at 0.5, 1, and 2 h), diluted 5-fold in saline, and transferred onto nutrient LB-agar plates. All plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h, and the colonies were counted. The reduction rate (δ , %) was determined as $\delta = 100 \times (C_0 - C) / C_0$, where the C_0 and C are bacterial colonies of blank and culture containing nanoparticle-cellulose, respectively. The blank was the culture without composite. Experiments were done in biological duplicates.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Enzymatic synthesis of reducing end thiol-modified nanocellulose

We have previously demonstrated two-phosphorylase cascade reaction for bottom-up synthesis of cello-oligosaccharides in a degree of polymerization (DP) of ~ 10 (Zhong et al., 2019). The cello-oligosaccharides self-assemble into a solid material with highly ordered cellulose II crystal structure (Zhong et al., 2019). Using CcCdP in combination with CuCbP, the biocatalytic synthesis can start from glucose (or derivatives thereof) as acceptor for the iterative β -1,4-glycosylation from $\alpha\text{Glc1-P}$. The CcCdP alone uses glucose inefficiently (0.07 U/mg protein; 0.5% of the specific activity on cellobiose (Zhong et al., 2019)) so that the cello-oligosaccharide synthesis would have to start from cellobiose. For the preparation of reducing end thiol-modified cellulose chains, the 1-thio- β -D-glucose is an interesting starting material that is commercially available. The CuCbP was active with 1-thio- β -D-glucose, although the specific activity (0.63 ± 0.08 U/mg; $n = 2$) was lower ($\sim 2\%$) as compared to that with glucose. The CuCbP requires the β -anomeric OH of glucose for hydrogen bonding with the enzyme (Hidaka et al., 2006; Nidetzky, Eis, & Albert, 2000). Replacement of the β -anomeric OH by H or F largely destroys the enzyme activity (Nidetzky et al., 2000). The relatively low activity with 1-thio- β -D-glucose is consistent with the expectation that the β -anomeric thiol group can only poorly substitute for the original β -OH group in providing a hydrogen for bonding with the enzyme. The CcCdP was only weakly active with 1-thio- β -D-glucose, showing a specific activity (7.6 ± 0.8 mU/mg; $n = 2$) about 83-fold lower compared to CuCbP. These results support the idea of a two-enzyme cascade reaction using CuCbP and CcCdP in combination. Although used before to synthesize reducing end-modified celluloses (Adharis, Petrović, Özdamar, Woortman, & Loos, 2018; de Andrade et al., 2021; Yataka, Sawada, & Serizawa, 2015), the single-enzyme CcCdP reaction with 1-thio- β -D-glucose would require excessive loadings of protein catalyst to proceed efficiently.

The biocatalytic synthesis was performed using 100 mM $\alpha\text{Glc1-P}$ and 10 mM 1-thio- β -D-glucose. Earlier studies have shown that in order to prepare insoluble cellulose in good yield, the molar ratio of donor and acceptor should be around ~ 10 or higher (Petrovic, Kok, Woortman, Circ, & Loos, 2015; Zhong et al., 2019). Cello-oligosaccharides of $\text{DP} \geq 7$ are hardly soluble in water and the DP distribution of the oligosaccharide products is largely controlled by the donor/acceptor ratio (Zhong & Nidetzky, 2019; Zhong et al., 2019). The CcCdP (80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) was used in slight (1.3-fold) excess over CuCbP, with the idea that incipient 1-thio- β -D-cellobiose formed by the CuCbP can be rapidly elongated by the CcCdP. By way of confirmation, we also performed the single-enzyme reaction using otherwise exactly identical conditions but lacking the CuCbP. We show in Figure S2 (Supplementary material) that both the reaction of CuCbP-CcCdP and of CcCdP alone produced insoluble cellulose from 1-thio- β -D-glucose. However, the yield of $\alpha\text{Glc1-P}$ converted (~ 41 mol.%) in the CuCbP-CcCdP reaction at 12 h exceeded the yield in the CcCdP reaction at 48 h by ~ 3.5 -fold. About 70% of the cello-oligosaccharide products formed in the CuCbP-CcCdP reaction was found in the solid precipitate. Previous studies of the synthesis of unmodified cellulose using CuCbP and CcCdP have suggested strategies to enhance the yield: one involves in situ removal of the phosphate released from $\alpha\text{Glc1-P}$ by precipitation with Mg^{2+} (Zhong et al., 2019); the other involves the continuous supply of donor $\alpha\text{Glc1-P}$, via in situ

conversion of sucrose and phosphate catalyzed by sucrose phosphorylase (Zhong & Nidetzky, 2019; Zhong, Ukowitz, Domig, & Nidetzky, 2020). Both strategies might be applied to the synthesis of thiol-modified cello-oligosaccharides. However, intensification of biocatalytic synthesis was outside of the scope of the current, conceptual study and was therefore left for consideration in the future.

3.2. Structural characterization of the thiol group-modified nanocellulose

The thiol-cellulose was dissolved at alkaline conditions in 4% (w/w) NaOD-D₂O and analyzed by ¹H-NMR. The spectra showed signals assigned to the repeating β-glucosyl units of the cello-oligosaccharides (Fig. 2A) (Isogai, 1997). The dominant doublet at around δ_H 4.30 was assigned to the internal β-1,4 glycosidic linkages (Hiraishi et al., 2009; Petrovic et al., 2015). By reference to the acceptor substrate, the doublet signal at δ_H 4.35 (*J*-coupling constant of 8.9 Hz) corresponds to the anomeric proton (H₁) of the terminal β-1-thio-glucose residue in the thiol-cellulose chain. However, there were additional signals at δ_H 5.12 and 4.53 which, according to previous studies of cello-oligosaccharides (Hiraishi et al., 2009; Serizawa et al., 2016; Zhong et al., 2019), are assigned to the α- and β-anomeric proton at the plain cello-oligosaccharide reducing end, respectively. From the integral signals of the anomeric protons, we determined that the thiol-cellulose accounted for ~61% of the total material synthesized. In addition, we characterized the synthetic material by MALDI-TOF-MS. As shown in Fig. 2B, the mass spectra showed a series of peaks with peak-to-peak mass difference of 162 Da, corresponding to expected mass of a single glucosyl unit (Petrovic et al., 2015; Serizawa et al., 2016). There were two groups of peaks in the spectra which based on their *m/z* values were assigned to cello-oligomers of DP 6–11 containing or lacking a single thiol group. The mass difference between cello-oligosaccharides featuring normal and thiol-modified reducing end was +16 *m/z* (-OH compared to -SH). Larger mass differences observed in the spectra were explainable on account of gradual oxidation of the terminal thiol group into sulfenic acid (-SOH; +32 *m/z*), sulfinic acid (-SO₂H; +48 *m/z*) and sulfonic acid (-SO₃H; +64 *m/z*). Recent study (Gaillot, Fabre, Charreyre, Ladavière, & Favier, 2020) shows such oxidations to occur on thiol groups in MALDI-TOF MS analysis. From the overall mass peak intensities of plain and modified cello-oligosaccharides, we estimated the content of thiol-cellulose in total synthetic material to be ~64%, consistent with the results of ¹H NMR analysis.

To identify the origin of the unlabeled cellulose, we first analyzed the

substrate purity, considering that contaminating D-glucose would give rise to the synthesis of plain cellulose. Only trace amounts of D-glucose were found in the commercial preparations of αGlc1-P and 1-thio-β-D-glucose, and the D-glucose carried over to the synthetic reaction was maximally 0.1 mM. Polymerization of that D-glucose would have given just ~1% unlabeled cellulose in total solid mass recovered from the reaction, inconsistent with the evidence. We thus considered that D-glucose might be released in larger amounts if one of the enzymes used showed hydrolase activity against the αGlc1-P substrate. Offering αGlc1-P (100 mM) in the absence of acceptor and measuring phosphate release, we found that the CuCbP was inactive below detection limit (≤ 0.1 mU/mg) but the CcCdP showed weak activity (20.7 ± 0.4 mU/mg, n = 2). The αGlc1-P hydrolase activity corresponded to ~0.15% of the synthetic activity of CcCdP recorded under identical conditions in the presence of cellobiose (50 mM) (Zhong et al., 2019). We considered that αGlc1-P hydrolysis might arise due to CcCdP exhibiting intrinsically a low level of glycoside hydrolase activity towards this substrate; or because the CcCdP preparation used contained trace amount of contaminating phosphatase activity. We assayed the CcCdP with 4-nitro-phenyl-phosphate (10 mM) which is a common phosphatase substrate. The CcCdP was completely inactive, despite high protein concentrations (1.5 mg/mL) and long reaction times (24 h) used in the assay. We showed the D-glucose released by CcCdP during cellulose synthesis could be as high as ~3.0 mM (Supplementary material S3), which accounts reasonably for the portion of unlabeled cellulose detected in the insoluble material. Due to the substrate specificity of CuCbP, as shown above, the enzymatic rates of synthesis of β-1-thio-cellobiose and cellobiose might be comparable under these conditions. Complications due to probably intrinsic αGlc1-P hydrolase activity of the CcCdP notwithstanding, the synthetic cellulose composed of ~64% thiol-cellulose was well suited for our inquiry, as shown below. Where relevant, we used plain cellulose obtained through the same synthetic procedure as the reference.

Based on the ¹H NMR profile, comparison of signal intensities of the anomeric protons at internal (δ_H 4.30) and terminal (δ_H 4.35) positions was used to obtain an estimate of 8.6 ± 0.3 for the average DP of 1-thio-β-cello-oligosaccharides (Supplementary material S4). From the intensities of the thiol-cellulose peaks in the MALDI-TOF-MS spectra, the average DP was estimated as 8.1 (Supplementary material S4). It is in agreement with literature (Petrovic et al., 2015; Serizawa et al., 2016) that the NMR-determined average DP was slightly higher than the MS-determined average DP. Tentatively, the effect could arise from the difficulty of ionizing higher-DP cello-oligomers. In addition, the plain

Fig. 2. Structure characterization of the synthetic, reducing-end β-thiol-labeled cellulose: A) ¹H-NMR profile (i, 1-thio-β-D-glucose; ii, thiol-modified cellulose, with inset showing the enlarged region for the anomeric protons); and B) MALDI-TOF MS spectra of the synthetic cellulose. For each DP, the peak of plain cello-oligomer is indicated by asterisk *. The cluster of mass peaks showing mass increase of +16/32/48/64 *m/z* compared to the mass of the plain cello-oligomer was assigned to the thiol-modified cello-oligomer (+16 *m/z*) and the corresponding oxidized species (+32 *m/z*, -SOH; +48 *m/z*, -SO₂H; +64 *m/z*, -SO₃H). The material was synthesized from CbP-CdP cascade reaction under the condition: 100 mM αGlc1-P, 10 mM 1-thio-β-D-glucose in MES buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0) containing 0.06 mg/mL of CuCbP and 0.08 mg/mL of CcCdP, 45 °C, 12 h.

cellulose had an estimated average DP of 7.7.

We also performed elemental analysis of the synthetic thiol-cellulose material and find a C/S mass ratio of 27.72 ± 0.45 . Assuming the average DP of 8.1–8.6, this value was in good agreement with the estimated abundance of thiol-cellulose (~64%) in total synthetic material (Supplementary material S4). Overall, therefore, the average DP of thiol-cellulose was comparable with the average DP of oligosaccharides obtained from β -1,4-glycosylation of unmodified glucose (Hiraishi et al., 2009; Petrovic et al., 2015; Serizawa et al., 2016; Zhong et al., 2019). The results confirm the expected chemical structure of the cello-oligosaccharides prepared from 1-thio- β -D-glucose.

The thiol-cellulose material was further characterized by EDXS spectra, XRD patterns, and ATR-FTIR absorption spectroscopy. As shown in Fig. 3A, besides the peaks of carbon (C) and oxygen (O) that were observed in the EDXS spectra of both thiol-modified and plain cellulose, the thiol-cellulose showed a unique peak (~2.3 keV) assigned to sulfur (S). This result further confirmed the presence of thiol groups in the synthetic material. The XRD patterns showed diffraction peaks (2θ at 12.3° , 20.0° , and 22.1°) that can be assigned from previous studies to the $1\bar{1}0$, 110 and 020 faces of crystalline cellulose II (Fig. 3B), respectively (Hori & Wada, 2006). The sharp peaks indicate a highly crystalline material. The ATR-FTIR spectra show characteristic peaks at 3441 and 3490 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3C), and these absorption bands are typical of the -OH

stretching intramolecular hydrogen bonds presented in crystalline cellulose II and are not observed in cellulose I crystal structure (Carrillo, Colom, Suñol, & Saurina, 2004; Nelson & O'Connor, 1964). Taken together, the structural parameters for the reducing-end thiol-modified cellulose strongly support a cellulose II allomorph in the material. The diffraction patterns from XRD and the spectra from ATR-FTIR are almost superimposable for the materials synthesized from 1-thio- β -D-glucose and glucose. The presence of the β -anomeric thiol group seems not to interfere with the self-assembly driven organization of the cellulose chains into crystalline material.

The morphologies of the cellulose material were microscopically observed. As shown in Fig. 3D, AFM observation revealed that the synthesized cellulose oligomers were assembled into nanosheet crystals in width of up to ~100 nanometers and length of several micrometers. Interestingly, in most cases, these nanosheet crystals were found to form a ribbon-shaped structure. We assumed that, under the conditions used for synthesis, the sheet-like crystals were prevented from precipitation due to decreased hydrophobic and self-crowding effects (Hata, Sawada, Marubayashi, Nojima, & Serizawa, 2019), and that they would continue to grow, stack on each other through physical crosslinking (Navarra et al., 2015), and eventually form into the ribbon-like structure as shown in Fig. 3D. It was reported that the thickness of nanocellulose was defined by the DP and the crystal allomorph of oligomers, at sub-ten

Fig. 3. Characterization of the synthetic, reducing-end β -thiol-labeled cellulose: A) EDXS profile, with plain cellulose shown with dashed line, B) XRD patterns, C) ATR-FTIR spectra, and D) AFM image of the crystalline thiol-modified nanocellulose. The material was synthesized from CbP-CdP cascade reaction under the condition: 100 mM α Glc1-P, 10 mM 1-thio- β -D-glucose in MES buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0) containing 0.06 mg/mL of CuCbP and 0.08 mg/mL of CcCdP, 45 °C, 12 h.

nanometer scales (Serizawa, Fukaya, & Sawada, 2017). Here, the thickness of the material was in a range of 5–7 nm according to the cross-sectional AFM analysis (Supplementary material S5), and it is comparable to the chain length of 10 with cellulose II allomorph (5.2 nm) (Yataka et al., 2015). Taken together, AFM data suggest that the synthesized oligomers were likely to align perpendicularly to the base plane of nanosheet/-ribbon. Considering that antiparallel cellulose II crystals are formed via self-assembly of the oligomers, it is reasonably suggested that the functional thiol groups (on the reducing end of the cellulose oligomers) are regularly distributed on the two base planes (surface) of the cellulose nanosheets, as illustrated in Fig. 1B.

3.3. Assembly of Ag nanoparticles on the thiol group-modified nanocellulose

The presence of reducing-end β -thiol groups on the cellulose chains whose crystalline organization involves antiparallel chain orientation endows the synthetic nanocellulose with unique properties for the controlled assembly of Ag nanoparticles (An et al., 2019). A modular approach of nanocomposite preparation is supported in which the thiol-cellulose is used as a separate pre-fabricated entity and the nanoparticle assembly process is decoupled from their synthesis. The thiol groups on the cellulose can promote a surface-dispersed, covalent attachment of Ag nanoparticles (An et al., 2019). Here, the nanoparticles were used without prior surface modification. However, attachment of monolayer-protected nanoparticles should likewise be possible. It could occur via exchange of the monolayer with functionalized thiol groups on

Fig. 4. Characterization of Ag nanoparticle assembly on the thiol-modified nanocellulose. A) UV-vis absorption spectra of the supernatants from Ag nanoparticle assembly within 1–5 min. 0.42 mg thiol-cellulose (dry weight) suspended into 1 mL Ag nanoparticle colloidal solution was set for the analysis; B) XRD patterns and C-D) AFM images (left panel, two-dimensional height image; right panel, three-dimensional visualization of the left-panel image) of the Ag nanoparticle-cellulose composite, prepared from Ag nanoparticle assembly under the above condition for 5 min.

the cellulose, as demonstrated in studies of thiol-based conjugation of metal nanoparticles in other polymer materials (Haidari et al., 2020; Mahato et al., 2019).

The Ag nanoparticles were synthesized as a colloidal solution using a modified Frens method (Gakiya-Teruya et al., 2018) based on reduction of Ag^+ with citrate. The nanoparticles were characterized by UV-vis spectroscopy. Maximum absorption peak at ~ 410 nm (Fig. 4A) indicated the Ag nanoparticles formed (Rucha et al., 2012). Peak analysis in terms of the full width at half maximum suggested a relatively narrow distribution of the Ag nanoparticle size. The AFM data (Fig. 4D) revealed spherical nanoparticles with a diameter of approximately 20–50 nm.

Binding of the Ag nanoparticles (~ 1 mM; based on the initial AgNO_3 reduced) to thiol-cellulose (0.42 mg/mL; 0.28 mM based on 1-thio- β -cello-nonaose) was monitored from the decrease in absorbance at 410 nm in solution and shown to proceed to completion within ~ 5 min (Fig. 4A). The yield of Ag nanoparticle-nanocellulose composite was thus quantitative (100% binding efficiency, Fig. 5B). XRD analysis of the composite material confirmed the incorporation of Ag. Two diffraction peaks at 2θ of 38° and 44° were observed from the composite (Fig. 4B), but were not present in the reference material lacking Ag. From previous studies, the peaks at 2θ of 38° and 44° are assigned to the (111) and (200) planes of Ag, respectively (Drogat et al., 2011). The diffraction patterns assigned to crystalline cellulose II were largely unaltered in the Ag nanoparticle-loaded sample as compared to the reference. This suggests that binding of the Ag nanoparticles does not change the nanoscale ordered structure of the synthetic cellulose. Moreover, the dispersion properties of the nanocellulose were retained after loading of the Ag

nanoparticles (Supplementary material S6), thus ensuring efficient use of the composite material(s) for different applications. We consider the results important in light of alternative procedures for the fabrication of nanoparticle-cellulose composites that may involve substantial changes in the cellulose structure. For example, direct synthesis of Ag nanoparticles on the cellulose surface requires extensive modification (e.g., chemical derivatization such as oxidation (Drogat et al., 2011; Ifuku, Tsuji, Morimoto, Saimoto, & Yano, 2009); or coating with polymers (Niu, Hua, & Xu, 2020; Xu et al., 2017)) of the cellulose to promote Ag^+ adsorption. Besides Ag nanoparticle aggregation, control of cellulose morphology can be difficult under these conditions.

The thiol-cellulose loaded with Ag nanoparticles from Fig. 4A was analyzed by AFM. Images shown in Fig. 4C/D reveal the Ag nanoparticles well dispersed on the surface of cellulose nanosheets. The cellulose structure was well preserved while the smooth surface of nanosheets became irregular after the binding with Ag nanoparticles, which existed as small, mostly spherical objects. These nanoparticles were rather uniform in size (diameter of 20–50 nm) and their distribution on the surface involved interparticle distances ≥ 50 nm. Noticeable nanoparticles agglomeration was not observed. Predicted function of thiol-cellulose in templating the Ag nanoparticles is thus confirmed. Besides, the AFM images indicate that a significant portion of the cellulose surface remained unoccupied with nanoparticles (Fig. 4D). It is worth noting therefore that, as shown below, the composite material analyzed represented just 1/8 of the maximum binding capacity of the thiol-cellulose for Ag nanoparticles. High surface density of the Ag nanoparticles can probably be reached by assembling them into the

Fig. 5. Comparison of Ag nanoparticle assembly on the cellulose featuring the thiol modification (+ thiol) or lacking it (– thiol). **A**) Images showing the Ag nanoparticle assembly: 1, 0.42 mg cellulose material incubated into 1 mL colloidal suspension of Ag nanoparticles for 5 min (+ thiol) or 1 h (– thiol); 2, after centrifugation ($1500 \times g$, 1 min); 3, resuspension of the pellets (on vortex mixer, 2500 rpm) for 5 min and immediate centrifugation ($1500 \times g$, 1 min). **B**) Time course of Ag nanoparticle binding using thiol-modified cellulose (+ thiol, 0.05–0.42 mg) mixed with 1 mL colloidal suspension; **C**) Time course of binding and release (after resuspension) of Ag nanoparticles using unmodified cellulose (– thiol, 0.42 mg) mixed with 1 mL colloidal suspension.

organized matrix of the thiol-cellulose.

Time courses of Ag nanoparticle binding were recorded at varied nanoparticle/thiol-cellulose loadings, resulting from the changes in cellulose concentration in experiment. The binding took longer (up to 30 min) as the loading of cellulose decreased, as shown in Fig. 5B, but was almost quantitative in each case. Using the unmodified cellulose, we found that nanoparticle binding was much slower (hours compared to minutes) and less complete (Fig. 5C). Unmodified cellulose binds Ag nanoparticles in a rather non-selective manner via its hydroxy groups (Meng, Lai, Jiang, Zhao, & Zhan, 2013; Musino et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020). However, such binding is not very efficient (Chou, Wu, Lin, & Rick, 2014). It is not well controllable and considerably weaker than binding via thiol groups. Here, we show in Fig. 5A that the Ag nanoparticle binding on thiol-cellulose was much more stable mechanically than it was on unmodified cellulose. Incubation on vortex mixer (2500 rpm, 5 min) released the non-selectively bound nanoparticles in large

amount (~24%, Fig. 5C) whereas the release from thiol-cellulose was hardly detectable ($\leq 1\%$) under the same treatment (data not shown). The expected functionality of β -thiol groups in the stable binding of Ag nanoparticles is thus confirmed. The high binding capacity of the thiol-cellulose (2.2 g Ag/g thiol-cellulose; equivalent to 27.4–29.1 mol Ag/mol thiol-cellulose with an assumed average DP of 8.1–8.6) is promising to create hybrid materials featuring a densely arrayed, stable layer of surface-assembled nanoparticles.

3.4. Antibacterial activity of the nanoparticle composite with thiol-cellulose

The antibacterial activity of Ag nanoparticles assembled on thiol-cellulose was assessed in agar diffusion test as well as in bacterial suspension culture. *S. aureus* and *E. coli* were selected for their widespread use in related literature (Jung et al., 2008), representing the class of

Fig. 6. Antibacterial activity of Ag nanoparticles in colloidal or thiol-cellulose-bound form against **A)** *E. coli* and **B)** *S. aureus* (sub 1, agar-plate test; sub 2, shake-flask test). In agar-plate test, the numbered circles present the area loaded with 10 μ L of 1, colloidal solution of Ag nanoparticles; 2, sterilized water; 3, Ag nanoparticle-cellulose suspension; and 4, thiol-cellulose suspension. In shake-flask test, time-course reduction of bacteria incubated in the presence of Ag nanoparticle-cellulose composite (5 g/L) was shown, and the control was incubation without nanoparticle-cellulose composite added.

Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, respectively. Colloidal Ag nanoparticles (loaded in the same amount) were used as the reference and as the control, the metal-free thiol-cellulose was used. As shown in Fig. 6, the Ag nanoparticles in colloidal and thiol-cellulose-bound form exhibited strong activity against both organisms. On agar plate, distinct eradication of bacterial colonies was observed in the areas loaded. Based on the colony reduction in the clearance zone, both delivery forms of the Ag nanoparticles appeared to be similarly effective under the conditions used. Interestingly, the thiol-cellulose control showed a slightly positive effect on bacterial growth on the agar plate. However, advantage of the nanoparticles assembled on thiol-cellulose was revealed after storage. The composite showed excellent retention of its efficacy over 14 days while the colloidal suspension lost it gradually within the same time (Supplementary material S7), probably in consequence of nanoparticle agglomeration (Bae et al., 2010). We note that besides concentration, the antibacterial activity of Ag nanoparticles also depends on size, with the general trend that smaller particles are more efficacious (Haidari et al., 2020; Raza et al., 2016). Being more agglomeration-prone than larger particles (Bae et al., 2010; Raza et al., 2016), the small nanoparticles are expected to benefit in particular from a thiol group-directed assembly on cellulose. As already mentioned, decoupling of the nanoparticle synthesis from polymer template fabrication offers modularity for the preparation of the nanoparticle-cellulose hybrid materials. The nanoparticle-cellulose composites can thus provide a controlled and localized delivery platform for the antibacterial activity of Ag. The antibacterial activity of the Ag nanoparticles assembled on thiol-cellulose was further confirmed in the suspension culture of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (Supplementary material S8). Reduction of the vegetative cell count was more significant for *E. coli* than *S. aureus* in short incubation time (≤ 0.5 h), but eventually both microorganisms were inactivated completely (Fig. 6). The difference in sensitivity could be explained by the efficiency of Ag nanoparticles interacting with different structures of bacterial cell wall, where Gram-positive bacteria possess a peptidoglycan layer that is much thicker (~ 80 nm, thus more resistant to the action of Ag nanoparticles) than that of Gram-negative bacteria (~ 8 nm) (Dakal, Kumar, Majumdar, & Yadav, 2016; Slavina, Anis, Häfeli, & Bach, 2017). Overall, the potential of this composite as Ag-supported antibacterial material was revealed, and it would be promising to the applications such as wound dressing, food packaging, and personal care product.

4. Conclusions

We have developed a bi-enzymatic cascade reaction of CuCbP and CcCdP for bottom-up synthesis of reducing end thiol-labeled cellulose material. We showed that chemical homogeneity of the final material ($\sim 64\%$ thiol-cellulose, $\sim 36\%$ plain cellulose) is limited by enzyme selectivity for using α Glc1-P on the part of the CcCdP. Structurally, the synthetic thiol-cellulose is highly similar to plain cellulose prepared enzymatically under comparable conditions. We demonstrate functionality of the synthetic thiol-cellulose in directing the controlled assembly of Ag nanoparticles. We show the biocidal efficacy of the composite material. Generally, the synthetic thiol-cellulose offers versatility in application to different composite materials, due to the great modularity of the thiol group in promoting site-specific chemical interactions for controllable uses in templating. This can support bottom-up approaches by chemical design to the fabrication of new functional cellulose nanocomposites. For example, the thiol-cellulose could be used for the specific immobilization of gold nanoparticles (Guo et al., 2016; Nohara et al., 2019) to promote promising applications in catalysis and electrochemistry (Van Rie & Thielemans, 2017). Synthetic thiol-containing nanocellulose can thus expand the scope of cellulose materials beyond the reach of current top-down technologies.

Data accessibility statement

Data obtained in the current study are available from the DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4361484>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Chao Zhong: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Visualization. **Krisztina Zajki-Zechmeister:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation. **Bernd Nidetzky:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2021.117772>.

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